

FACTORS OF CHILD DEVELOPMENT IN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

Kambaralieva Durдона Asqarali kizi

Speech therapy, 3rd level student at Namangan State Pedagogical Institute,
Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology, Special pedagogy

Vakhobova Munirakhan Sadirdinovna

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology Namangan State
Pedagogical Institute Faculty of Pedagogy

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada inklyuziv ta’limda bolalarni har tomonlama psixologik, tibbiy, individual, jismoniy, aqliy, estetik jihatdan rivojlantirish omillari va ularning yechimlari tahlili haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: irsiyat, muhit, oʻzgaruvchanlik, individual yondashuv, logopedlar, integratsion muhit, inklyuziv ta’lim.

Аннотация: В статье подробно описан анализ факторов всестороннего психологического, медицинского, индивидуального, физического, психического и эстетического развития детей в условиях инклюзивного образования и пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: наследственность, среда, изменчивость, индивидуальный подход, логопеды, интегрированная среда, инклюзивное образование.

Annotation: This article describes in detail the analysis of the factors of comprehensive psychological, medical, individual, physical, mental, and aesthetic development of children in inclusive education and their solutions.

Key words: heredity, environment, variation, individual approach, speech therapists, integrated environment, inclusive education.

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education is an educational system in which children with disabilities or special needs can study and develop in the same conditions as other members of

society. The main goal of this system is to create equal educational opportunities for all children and their successful integration into social life. The process of child development in inclusive education is based on creating equal opportunities for each child and taking into account their individual needs. This process aims to ensure the same conditions for children with disabilities or special educational needs as for children in general education. Inclusive education promotes children's academic, social and psychological development.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

For this article, the following works were taken as a methodological basis. Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion. Routledge by Ainscow, M., Booth, T., Dyson, A. provides information on the principles of inclusive education and practical approaches to its implementation. Slee, R. "The Irregular School: Exclusion, Schooling, and Inclusive Education. Routledge." In his work, he covers the issues of social justice, equality and child support in inclusive education.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The main areas of development of children in inclusive education:

1. Equal access to education: Every child, regardless of disability, has the right to equal education. This is a key factor in their academic development.

2. Individual development plan: An educational program tailored to the individual needs of each child is developed, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses. This helps them realize their full potential.[1]

3. Social integration: Inclusive education develops children's social skills. Children socialize by interacting with their peers, doing team work, and feel part of the community.

4. Supportive environment: The supportive environment created by teachers and parents plays an important role in the psychological development of children. In this, the child's self-confidence increases and he participates more actively in the educational process.[2]

5. Pedagogical adaptations: Teachers organize education according to the needs of children using different pedagogical approaches. Special teaching methods, technologies and tools adapt the educational process to children.

6. Continuous evaluation and monitoring: It is important to constantly monitor the development of children, evaluate their progress in the learning process and make changes when necessary. This helps to increase the rate of development.[3]

Inclusive education ensures the personal, academic and social development of children by providing equal opportunities for development and focusing on the unique needs of each child. Through this system, children can feel themselves as active members of society and lead a successful life in the future.[4]

Inclusive education provides an important foundation for children's development through various factors.

1. Individual approach:

An individual approach plays an important role in the development of children. Since each child's needs and abilities are different, educators must develop an approach that suits them. For example, education on the basis of an individual plan, organization of lessons taking into account the child's unique capabilities, has a positive effect on his development.

2. Creating a supportive environment:

It is important that children feel safe and supported in an inclusive education system. For this, it is necessary to inspire the community in the school and classroom environment, show kindness to children and increase their self-confidence. A supportive environment helps the child realize his full potential.

3. Use of special pedagogical methods:

In inclusive education, pedagogues should use special educational methods adapted to the needs of children. These methods include interactive lessons, visual materials, individual and group training, and additional assistive technologies. Special methods help children to accept the educational process more easily.

4. Family and social cooperation:[5]

Families play an important role in improving the effectiveness of inclusive education. Cooperation between parents and teachers should be strengthened. At the same time, social organizations and society should also support the development of children and support the ideas of inclusive education.

5. Development of social adaptation and abilities:

One of the main tasks of inclusive education is to teach children social adaptation skills. This, in turn, ensures the successful integration of children into society. Through group games, various social projects and activities, children's communication skills, teamwork and sense of responsibility are developed.

6. Use of educational technologies:

Modern educational technologies play a major role in inclusive education. With the help of audio-video materials, online platforms and other modern technological tools, the educational process of children can be more effective. These tools can make a child's reading more interesting and understandable.[6]

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Child development factors in inclusive education are multifaceted and require an approach tailored to the needs of each child. This system not only helps children to learn, but also helps them find their place in society, gain self-confidence and develop as full-fledged individuals.

Inclusive education creates effective opportunities for children's development. This system ensures that all children have an equal right to education and promotes their personal, social, and academic development. The main directions of inclusive education include taking into account the specific needs of children, creating an environment that supports them, cooperation with families and society, and the use of modern pedagogical methods. This system helps each child successfully integrate into society.

As a suggestion for this article, we can include the following:

1. Creating more opportunities: Schools and educational institutions should be provided with facilities adapted to children with disabilities or special needs. This also includes providing all teachers with special training courses on inclusive education.

2. Improving Pedagogical Approaches: Teachers should adapt their teaching methods to the needs of each child. Through interactive and individual approaches, children's interest in education is increased and the rate of development is increased.

PROPOSALS

1. Creating more opportunities: Schools and educational institutions should be provided with facilities adapted to children with disabilities or special needs. This also includes providing all teachers with special training courses on inclusive education.

2. Improving Pedagogical Approaches: Teachers should adapt their teaching methods to the needs of each child. Through interactive and individual approaches, children's interest in education is increased and the rate of development is increased.

3. Regular cooperation with families: Families play a major role in children's development. Therefore, special trainings and informative events should be held for parents, and their active participation in the educational process should be ensured.

4. Creating a supportive and flexible environment: By creating a classroom environment where children feel safe and free, their self-confidence is increased. Each child's opinion should be valued and they should be helped to feel part of the community.

5. Continuous monitoring and evaluation: Every child's development should be monitored regularly and changes should be made by the teachers if necessary. In the assessment, it is recommended to use approaches aimed at developing the child's strengths.

6. Expanding the use of technologies: By using modern educational technologies, the educational process can be made more effective. The learning process of children should be supported with the help of interactive lessons, online platforms and special assistive technologies.

These proposals create additional opportunities for the full development of children in inclusive education, help each child find their place in society and develop their abilities.

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